

MAPPING INSIGHTS TO PRODUCT STRATEGY: EMOTIONAL TARGETS FOR THE FUTURE OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Our design and research firm partnered with a major educational publisher to understand the current state of learning in a college environment and gather insights about unmet needs. We sought to translate emotional insights into actionable ideas for their product. We created a map that connects key findings from the in-person student interviews and emotional targets, with the goal of informing the client's product development strategy for the Future of Learning.

Keywords: education, emotion, product, research, visualization

INTRODUCTION

Our design and research firm partnered with a major educational publisher to understand the current state of learning in a college environment and gather insights about unmet needs. Through this project—called the Future of Learning—the publisher sought new ways to address student needs, particularly through their online learning tool. The research was conducted using live, on-campus interviews to evaluate students' current learning experiences and what they might expect or hope for in the future learning landscape.

In the contextual interviews, students shared details about emotional aspects of learning, including relationships with teachers, interaction with peers, and their personal barriers and achievements. We translated these emotional insights into actionable ideas for the client's product. We created a map that connects key points from the in-person student

interviews with emotional targets, with the goal of informing the client's product development strategy.

After conducting 25 in-person student interviews, our research team combed through the transcripts of all of the student interviews, looking for common behaviors and comments, and grouped them into categories. We connected their behaviors not only to the emotions the students actually experienced in the circumstances they described, but also to target emotions—the ideal emotions for them to experience during a particular circumstance.

We then experimented with several ways to visualize this information. The final poster connects representative student quotes to behaviors and target emotions. These are tied to the current state of the client's product followed by recommendations for innovative new ways to meet student needs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We visited three college campuses and conducted interviews with 25 students. All interviewees were undergraduate students at the time of their interviews. Sessions were 10–20 minutes in length, depending upon the responses of the participants. Participants were asked

- general information about themselves and their majors.
- about their favorite teachers.
- about their ideal learning conditions.
- to imagine their learning context 5–10 years from now.

The interviews were both videotaped and audiotaped for further analysis.

SYNTHESIS METHODOLOGY

After transcribing the interview recordings, our research team combed the transcripts for common behaviors described by the students. Once a set of behaviors was identified, we looked for similarities and condensed them into groups, when possible. Representative student quotes were selected to illuminate the behaviors.

Emotions and emotional language were also noted, using categories based on the HUMAINE Emotion Annotation and Representation Language (EARL). We connected the emotions to respective behaviors. We interpreted students' language to determine a "Target Emotion" for each behavior. The behavior was linked to the client's existing feature set.

A recommendation was developed for each behavior, including references to specific software, tools and/or media.

VISUALIZATION DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1. A triad of behaviors related to the individual student, the instructor, and peers.

After determining the student quotes, behaviors, target emotions, and recommendations, we worked with the content to develop a form that best showed findings. One early attempt to visualize the materials included triangulating behaviors into categories of items related to the individual student, to the instructor, and to peers (Figure 1). Behaviors that were positive were placed inside the triangle;

destructive behaviors were placed outside the triangle.

In a second attempt to visualize findings, we created a variety of clusters. Through this visualization process, we were able to sort behaviors based on whether they take place inside or outside the classroom (or within either realm) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Creating relevant clusters.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Figure 4. The final poster connects student quotes, behaviors, and target emotions to product features and innovations.

Figure 3. A Venn diagram depicting behaviors grouped by inside classroom or outside classroom categories.

This inside-in or out-outside grouping carried into another visualization, in which behaviors and quotes were distributed in a Venn diagram and linked to features (Figure 3).

FINAL VISUALIZATION

REPRESENTATIVE STUDENT QUOTE

In the final poster (Figure 4), working down from the top, we selected a quote that represents each behavioral category, and an image of the student who provided the quote, pulled from his/her interview footage. Although not all 27 students are shown in the final poster, comments from all of the students contributed to the poster's categories of behaviors.

BEHAVIOR

The behaviors are grouped according to whether they occur inside the classroom (left group), in or out of the classroom (center), or generally happen outside of the classroom (right). We also indicated whether the behavior depended upon an interaction with an instructor (yellow), the student alone (green), or between classmates/peers (blue).

TARGET EMOTION(S)

The circular shapes describe target emotions: ideal states for students engaging in the above behaviors.

FEATURES

This section shows how the behaviors connect to existing feature categories. The yellow notes are commentary on the client's current product state relative to these student behaviors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This section includes future recommendations ideas and references to actualize student desires and push client further. Screenshots illustrate some examples relevant to the recommendations.

EXAMPLE

The poster includes eighteen columns of information, each starting with a student quote. Here is an example of one column to further illustrate the included materials.

REPRESENTATIVE STUDENT QUOTE

“We had to work as a group and it was really cool to take what the teacher was teaching and apply it to a group in reality and see it work. Our group ended up working really well together. I think during that time in that group, I really got into the flow of communication, working together, dividing responsibilities and everything, so that was definitely cool.”

BEHAVIOR

Peers collaborate on group projects.

TARGET EMOTION(S)

Confidence, interest.

FEATURES

Assignments and collaboration.

Current product state: [assignments] Currently, the tool only supports individual assignments. Instructors can edit existing assignments (homework, test, and quiz are all considered assignments) or create them from scratch. Students do these assignments within the system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Peers receive and submit group assignments as a group. They have resources to plan and visualize group projects. Similar to project planning tools like Basecamp and Roadmap, students have tools to assign specific tasks to individual members of their project teams, archive and search all communication (chats, emails, discussions), and clarify the roles and responsibilities of each member. Peers have access to “group meeting capture” features such as WebEx, as well as a way to record audio or video meetings and convert them to searchable transcripts.

PRODUCT RECOMMENDATIONS

We presented this poster to the client, along with additional high-level product recommendations. These recommendations summarized specific ideas from the poster and gave the client a guide for prioritizing future work. Each of these recommendations has a strong emotional component informed by target emotions from the visualization.

Recommendation 1: Incorporate features that support collaborative work as well as communication between students, groups, and the instructor.

Recommendation 2: Design for the class as a community. Features such as a class charter and online white boarding tools make the class feel like a cohesive group.

Recommendation 3: Personalization is important to learning. Students not only want to feel as though the instructor is connecting with them personally, but also need to be able to make connections between course content and their own lives. Furthermore, they want to see their classmates (and instructors) as real people. Getting to know each other facilitates social learning such as partner work, encouragement, and “study buddies.”

CONCLUSION

This project challenged our company to turn findings from open-ended contextual research into innovative ways to improve the future of learning. We found that emotion factors highly into the learning experience, and that students crave connection, community, and personalization.

It was important to our team to emphasize the emotional component of learning to our client, rather than simply providing feature recommendations. In order to show our client how behaviors and emotions relate to product innovations, we created a visualization that encompassed all of these elements.

We went through several rounds of exploration and drafts before determining the most useful and relevant aspects to include in the final visualization. The final artifact is a large-scale depiction that connects student

quotes to recommendations for future tools, centered around target emotions. As our client moves forward in rethinking how their tools can inform and improve the education experience, this map will serve as a guide and inspiration for new features, grounded in target emotions.

REFERENCE

HUMAINE emotion annotation and representation language (EARL); <http://emotion-research.net/projects/humaine/earl/proposal>. Accessed 6 February, 2012.